

JOSHI EFFECT IN BENZENE VAPOUR UNDER X-RAYS. PART II. INFLUENCE OF INTENSITY AND FREQUENCY

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The influence of fourteen-fold intensity (I) variation at a constant frequency (anode voltage), and at a constant intensity of a three-fold variation of frequency (ν_m) on Joshi effect, Δi , at a given exciting potential (V) is studied in ($p = 105$ mm.) benzene at 27° , excited by 8-16 kV (r. m. s.) of 50 μ . At constant V , with the progressive increase of I , $-\% \Delta i$ increases numerically almost linearly in the low I region, reaches a maximum at a critical I and decreases thereafter; and even changes sign at large I , a tendency favoured by a large V and low anode voltage. At constant I , $-\% \Delta i$ (as also $-\Delta i$) increases with the increasing frequency of X-rays.

The results are explained from the standpoint of the choking action of the positive ionic space charge. The relation $i = Q/t_a + t_m$, where Q is the charge during ($t_a + t_m$), t_a , the active time and t_m , the traversal time of the positive ions, is examined for the intensity and frequency variation of the X-radiation.

Data for the influence of intensity and especially frequency (*vide infra*) are of fundamental importance not only as quantitative determining factors of any light reaction, but to the elucidation of its mechanism. In the visible and also ultraviolet regions the difficulty of ensuring an independent and comparable intensity in widely separated frequency bands is well known. This limitation does not obtain appreciably in the case of X-radiations, yielded by a heated filament type emitter. Production of $\pm \Delta i$ (Part I, Asolkar, this issue, p. 233) in a typical organic compound like benzene vapour has more than an ordinary interest, as a hitherto unobserved fact. It was considered desirable therefore to study in some detail its variation over a wide range of intensity and frequency of incident radiation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general experimental procedure for the observation of Δi under X-rays in benzene vapour ($p = 105$ mm. at 27°) has been described earlier (Asolkar, *loc. cit.*). The Coolidge tube employed as a source of X-rays allowed of a variation of its tube current (anode current) from 0.7 mA; this current is considered a reasonably accurate measure of the intensity (I) of X-rays (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*). The anode voltage is expressed in kilovolts (r. m. s.). It is known that at a given voltage and tube current X-rays of various frequencies and intensities are produced and that the frequency position of maximum intensity is related simply to the anode voltage. The influence of X-ray frequency on the magnitude of Δi at a constant intensity was restricted to observation of its dependence on anode voltage as a first approximation (Rutherford, Barnes and Richardson, *Phil. Mag.*, 1915, 30, 339). This frequency (ν_m) as denoted by the anode voltage was varied from 10.8 to 26.3 kilovolts in steps of 3.1 kilovolts. The ozoniser charged with benzene vapour was excited over a fairly wide potential range. This exciting potential is denoted by kV (r. m. s.). The temperature of the system was maintained

constant within $\pm 3^\circ$ at 27° . This is a necessary precaution in view of the generally observed sensitivity of Δi to the temperature variation (Joshi and Deo, *Nature*, 1944, 158, 434; Mohanty, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 557; Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3924; Bhide, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1951, *Phy. Sec.*, Abs. No. 40). It is known that an 'ageing' effect is produced due to both (a) the discharge in absence of external radiation (Deo, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 21A, 76; Mallikarjunappa, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 197; Deshmukh, *ibid.*, 1949, 26, 176) and (b) exposure to X-rays (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 278) which affect sensibly the magnitude of Δi . This was minimised by limiting the former period to less than half a minute and that for X-rays to five seconds. In a given series of V— i characteristics the total amount of exposure seldom exceeded eight minutes and one minute in the two periods respectively. Further, the value of Δi at the end of a given series agrees within $\pm 1\%$ to that at the commencement of the series indicating that any variation due to either type of 'ageing' is inappreciable. These results are recorded in Tables I, II and III, in part shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2. Only a representative set of observations is shown, out of the results using ozonisers of different electrode spacings under widely varied operative conditions.

D I S C U S S I O N

Tables I-II and Fig. 1 show that $-\% \Delta i$ under X-rays increases with increasing intensity in the low intensity region. Thus, e. g., it rises from 1.3 to 14.6 for intensity variation from 0.1 mA to 1.5 mA tube current at a frequency corresponding to 10.8 kilovolts and 8.0 kV exciting potential. At a higher frequency such as 23.2 kilovolts the $-\% \Delta i$ shows the increase from 6.6 at 0.1 mA to 30.0 at 1.5 mA. Further increase in intensity yields a peak value for $-\% \Delta i$ between the intensity 2.0 mA and 2.5 mA. Thus, the peak values for 10.8 and 23.2 kilovolts X-rays are respectively -16.6% at 2.0 mA and -34% at 2.5 mA respectively. As the intensity is further increased $-\% \Delta i$ decreases slowly. Thus, between the intensities 3.0 and 7.0 mA the $-\% \Delta i$ decreased from 30.6 to 16.0 and from 14.0 to 2.0 for 23.2 and 10.8 kilovolts X-rays respectively at the exciting potential 8.0 kV.

For lower exciting voltage (e.g., 8 kV) and the frequency of X-rays corresponding to 10.8 kilovolts, the maximum $-\% \Delta i$ is 16.6 at 2 mA decreasing to -2.0% at 7.0 mA without changing sign. For higher values of V (such as 20.0 kV) and 23.2 kilovolts X-rays, the $-\% \Delta i$ rises from 1 to a maximum of 12.8 and decreases to 2.6 at 7 mA. In the X-ray region, the $-\% \Delta i$ at first increases rapidly with intensity, reaches a peak value and decreases slowly; for large V and at very high values of I, it changes sign yielding $+\Delta i$ (Table II and Fig. 1). Thus, for anode voltage 10.8 kilovolts, and exciting potential 20.0 kV, $-\% \Delta i$ increases from 0.3 to a peak value 3.0 for anode current 2.5 mA slowly decreasing to 0.6 at 5.5 mA changes sign at 6.0 mA (Table II) yielding $+0.3\% \Delta i$. Further increase in intensity to 7 mA anode current increases $\% \Delta i$ to $+1$. This inversion of $-\Delta i$ to $+\Delta i$ with intensity in the X-ray region is significant. This tendency is favoured by large I, and especially at large V and low anode voltage.

Extensive studies of the variation of Δi with light intensities in the various frequency bands have been made (Joshi *B. H. U. Jour.*, 1943, 8, 99; Joshi and Deo,

TABLE I

Influence of intensity of X-rays on the Joshi effect in benzene vapour at different frequencies and constant exciting potential.

pC ₆ H ₆ = 105 mm. at 27°.		Frequency of A.C. supply = 50 ~.										Source of X-radiations = Coolidge tube.																								
Frequency (anode-voltage in kilovolts).		Intensity (anode-current in mA).										Current in dark (i ₀) = 150 (arbitrary units).																								
		Exciting potential = 8.0 kV (r.m.s.).										Exciting potential = 20 kV (r.m.s.). i ₀ = 650.																								
Frequency	i ₀	0.1	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0	6.5	7.0	Frequency	i ₀	0.1	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0	6.5	7.0			
10.8	i ₀	148	140	133	128	125	127	129	133	136	130	141	143	145	146	147	130	122	115	108	101	94	87	80	73	66	59	52	45	38	31	24	17	10	3	
	-Δi	2	10	17	22	25	23	21	17	14	11	9	7	5	4	3	28	25	22	19	16	13	10	7	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	-%Δi	1.3	6.6	11.3	14.5	16.6	15.3	14.0	11.3	9.3	7.3	6.0	4.7	3.3	2.6	2.0	18.7	16.6	14.6	12.6	10.6	8.0	6.0	4.7	3.3	2.6	2.0	1.5	1.1	0.8	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.0	
13.9	i ₀	145	136	127	121	116	117	120	123	127	130	132	134	136	138	139	127	123	119	115	111	107	103	99	95	91	87	83	79	75	71	67	63	59	55	
	-Δi	5	14	23	29	34	33	30	27	23	20	18	16	14	12	11	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	-%Δi	3.3	9.3	15.3	19.3	22.6	22.6	20.0	18.0	15.3	13.3	12.0	10.6	9.3	8.0	7.3	15.3	13.3	11.5	10.6	9.3	8.0	7.3	6.0	5.0	4.0	3.2	2.6	2.0	1.5	1.1	0.8	0.5	0.3	0.2	
17.0	i ₀	144	133	124	118	112	111	112	115	119	122	125	128	131	132	134	119	115	111	107	103	99	95	91	87	83	79	75	71	67	63	59	55	51	47	
	-Δi	6	17	26	32	38	39	38	35	31	28	25	22	19	18	16	28	25	22	19	16	14	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	0
	-%Δi	4.0	11.3	17.3	21.3	25.3	26.0	25.3	23.3	20.6	18.7	16.6	14.6	12.6	12.0	10.7	23.3	20.6	18.7	16.6	14.6	12.6	11.5	10.6	9.3	8.0	7.3	6.0	5.0	4.2	3.4	2.6	2.0	1.5	1.1	
20.1	i ₀	143	131	121	114	109	105	107	111	115	118	121	123	125	128	130	115	111	107	103	99	95	91	87	83	79	75	71	67	63	59	55	51	47	43	
	-Δi	7	19	29	36	41	45	43	39	35	32	29	27	25	22	20	32	29	27	25	22	20	18	16	14	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2
	-%Δi	4.6	12.6	19.3	24.0	27.3	30.0	28.3	26.0	23.3	21.3	19.3	18.0	16.3	14.7	13.3	28.3	26.0	23.3	21.3	19.3	18.0	16.3	14.7	13.3	12.0	10.7	9.3	8.0	7.3	6.0	5.0	4.2	3.4	2.6	
23.2	i ₀	140	128	119	111	105	99	104	108	112	115	118	120	123	125	126	108	104	100	96	92	88	84	80	76	72	68	64	60	56	52	48	44	40	36	
	-Δi	10	22	31	39	45	51	46	41	38	35	32	30	27	25	24	38	35	32	29	27	25	22	20	18	16	14	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4
	-%Δi	6.5	14.7	20.7	26.0	30.0	34.0	30.6	28.0	25.3	23.3	21.3	20.0	18.0	16.7	16.0	34.0	30.6	28.0	25.3	23.3	21.3	20.0	18.0	16.7	15.0	13.0	11.0	10.0	9.0	8.0	7.0	6.0	5.0	4.0	
20.1	i ₀	645	625	608	594	581	576	584	593	602	610	617	624	629	633	636	602	584	568	552	536	520	504	488	472	456	440	424	408	392	376	360	344	328	312	
	-Δi	5	25	42	50	60	74	66	57	48	40	33	26	21	17	14	48	40	33	26	21	17	14	11	8	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	
	-%Δi	0.8	3.8	6.5	8.6	10.6	11.4	10.0	8.7	7.4	6.2	5.0	4.0	3.2	2.6	2.2	7.4	6.2	5.0	4.0	3.2	2.6	2.2	1.7	1.4	1.1	0.8	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	
23.2	i ₀	643	621	602	584	572	567	573	582	593	601	609	615	623	628	633	593	582	573	567	558	549	540	531	522	513	504	495	486	477	468	459	450	441	432	
	-Δi	7	29	48	66	78	83	77	68	57	49	41	35	27	22	17	57	49	41	35	27	22	17	13	10	8	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	0	0	0
	-%Δi	1.0	4.4	7.5	10.1	12.0	12.8	11.8	10.2	8.8	7.5	6.3	5.4	4.2	3.4	2.6	8.8	7.5	6.3	5.4	4.2	3.4	2.6	2.2	1.7	1.4	1.1	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.1	

TABLE II

Influence of intensity of X-rays on the Joshi effect in benzene vapour at different exciting potentials and constant frequency (anode voltage = 10.8 kilovolts).

$\mu\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 = 105 \text{ mm.}$ at 27° Frequency of A. C. supply = 50 ~ . Source of X-radiations = Coolidge tube.

Exciting potential in kV (r.m.s.).	Intensity (anode-current) in mA.															
	0.1	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0	6.5	7.0	
8	i_L	148	140	133	128	125	127	129	133	136	139	141	143	145	146	147
	Δi	2	10	17	22	25	23	21	17	14	11	9	7	5	4	3
	$-\% \Delta i$	1.3	6.6	11.3	14.6	16.6	15.3	14.0	11.3	9.3	7.3	6.0	4.7	3.3	2.6	2.0
10	i_L	227	221	213	208	204	207	212	215	218	220	222	224	225	226	227
	Δi	3	9	17	22	26	23	18	15	12	10	8	6	5	4	3
	$-\% \Delta i$	1.3	3.9	7.4	9.5	11.3	10.0	7.8	6.5	5.2	4.3	3.5	2.6	2.1	1.7	1.3
12	i_L	318	312	308	304	301	302	305	307	310	313	315	317	318	318	319
	Δi	2	8	12	16	19	18	15	13	10	7	5	3	2	2	1
	$-\% \Delta i$	0.6	2.5	3.8	5.0	5.9	5.6	4.7	4.0	3.1	2.2	1.5	0.9	0.6	0.6	0.3
14	i_L	393	392	387	384	381	382	385	388	390	393	395	397	398	398	399
	Δi	2	8	13	16	19	18	15	12	10	7	5	3	2	2	1
	$-\% \Delta i$	0.5	2.0	3.2	4.0	4.8	4.5	3.7	3.0	2.5	1.8	1.2	0.8	0.5	0.5	0.2
16	i_L	448	444	438	435	434	434	438	442	444	445	446	447	448	449	450
	Δi	2	6	12	15	18	16	12	8	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
	$-\% \Delta i$	0.4	1.3	2.6	3.3	4.0	3.3	2.7	1.7	1.3	1.1	0.9	0.6	0.4	0.2	0
18	i_L	529	524	516	512	509	511	515	518	521	525	526	528	530	531	533
	Δi	1	-6	14	18	21	19	15	12	9	5	4	2	0	+1	+3
	$\% \Delta i$	0.2	1.1	2.6	3.4	4.0	3.6	2.8	2.2	1.7	1.0	0.7	0.4	0.0	+0.2	+0.6
20	i_L	648	641	632	628	625	626	630	635	639	647	646	649	652	655	657
	Δi	2	9	18	22	25	24	20	15	11	7	4	1.0	+2.0	+5.0	+7.0
	$\% \Delta i$	0.3	1.4	2.7	3.3	3.8	3.6	3.0	2.3	1.7	1.0	0.6	-2.1	+0.1	+2.8	+1.0

TABLE III

Influence of frequency of X-rays on the Joshi effect in benzene vapour at different exciting potentials and constant intensity (anode current).

$p\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_6 = 105 \text{ mm. at } 27^\circ$. Frequency of A. C. supply = 50. Source of X-radiations = Coolidge tube.

Exciting Potential in kV (c.m.s.).	Current in dark fp.		2.0 mA				4.0 mA.							
			10.8	13.9	17.0	20.1	23.2	26.3	30.8	33.9	37.0	40.1		
8.0	150	i_L	125	116	112	109	105	100	136	127	119	115	112	108
		$-\Delta f$	25	34	38	41	45	50	14	23	31	35	38	42
		$-\% \Delta f$	16.6	22.6	25.3	27.3	30.0	33.3	9.3	15.3	20.6	21.3	25.3	28.0
10.0	230	i_L	204	193	186	182	176	173	218	207	196	190	185	177
		$-\Delta f$	26	37	44	48	54	57	12	23	34	40	45	53
		$-\% \Delta f$	11.3	16.0	19.0	20.8	23.5	24.3	5.2	10.0	14.8	17.4	19.6	23.2
12.0	320	i_L	301	283	273	266	258	254	310	298	285	277	270	261
		$-\Delta f$	19	37	47	54	62	66	10	24	35	43	50	59
		$-\% \Delta f$	5.1	11.5	14.7	16.9	19.3	21.2	3.1	6.8	10.9	13.4	15.6	18.2
14.0	400	i_L	381	366	351	343	339	336	390	378	366	361	352	344
		$-\Delta f$	19	34	49	57	61	64	10	22	34	39	48	56
		$-\% \Delta f$	4.8	8.5	12.3	14.2	15.2	16.0	2.5	5.4	8.5	9.8	12.0	14.0
16.0	450	i_L	434	417	405	406	389	386	444	431	418	404	398	390
		$-\Delta f$	18	33	45	54	61	64	6	19	32	46	52	60
		$-\% \Delta f$	4.0	7.3	10.0	12.0	13.6	14.2	1.3	4.2	7.1	10.2	11.5	13.3
18.0	530	i_L	509	494	479	471	464	460	521	509	492	483	476	467
		$-\Delta f$	21	36	51	59	66	70	9	21	38	47	54	63
		$-\% \Delta f$	4.0	6.7	9.6	11.1	12.4	13.2	1.7	4.0	7.2	8.8	10.1	11.9

Nature, 1943, 151, 561; Deo, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1944, 18, 84; *Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 44; Mohanty and Kamath, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 467; Prasad, *Nature*, 1949, 164, 69). The $-\% \Delta i$ in the visible increases initially almost linearly with light intensity and shows subsequently a tendency to saturation. Using various frequency bands in the visible, earlier workers have shown that $-\% \Delta i$ increases almost linearly with the mean frequency, despite an appreciable range of frequency variation (Deo, *loc. cit.* Tawde and Gopalkrishnan, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 29A, 171; Mohanty, *loc. cit.* Deshmukh, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, 1948, 25, 197).

As can be seen from Table III and Fig. 2, unlike this linear increase of $-\% \Delta i$ with frequency in the visible region, $-\% \Delta i$ at first increases rapidly with the hardness of X-radiation but later on the increase becomes slow. Thus, at a constant intensity (4 mA) the $-\% \Delta i$ increases numerically from 9.3 to 20.6 as the frequency of X-rays varies from 10.8 to 17.0 kilovolts; while for equal increment *i.e.* from 17.0 to 23.2 kilovolts, increase is, however, small *viz.* from 20.6 to 25.3, exciting potential being 8.0 kV. For the same frequency variation and exciting potential the corresponding values of $-\% \Delta i$ for 2.0 mA are 16.6 to 25.3 and from 25.3 to 30.0 respectively. The curves in Fig. 2 indicate clearly the variation of $-\% \Delta i$ with frequency at different exciting potentials.

The absorption of X-rays by the glass wall (1 mm.) of the ozoniser was considered. Series of experiments were made in which the $\% \Delta i$ values were recorded for various intensities at fixed exciting potentials without and with the glass screen (4 mm. thick) interposed between the Coolidge tube and the ozoniser. Results show that the $\% \Delta i - I$ curve with the glass screen is closely similar to that when no glass screen is used on (Fig. 1). The curve with the glass screen on, however, is just a little lower than the other curve due to the small X-ray absorption by glass. Similar duplicates show that the $\% \Delta i - v$ (hardness) with the glass screen also lies slightly lower than, but resembles essentially that without the screen (Fig. 2). No sensibly disturbing factor is therefore introduced in the discussion due to glass wall absorption.

Joshi has shown (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, 70; *B. H. U. Jour.*, 1943, 8, 99) on the basis of non-linearity of the $\% \Delta i - I$ relationship, that this phenomenon cannot be identified with a possible negative photoelectric effect. The results of Mohanty for oxygen (*loc. cit.*) and that of Prasad for mercury (*loc. cit.*) confirm Joshi's view. These results in the visible are fairly well explained by Joshi's theory (*Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 18, 19) according to which photoelectric emission from an electrode layer consisting of ions and excited particles, characterised by a low work function, is a primary seat of Δi ; the released photoelectrons are captured by gas particles in the discharge space to form slow moving negative ions which reduce the current i as a space charge effect.

That the Δi occurs under red region of the spectrum, which cannot photoionise the gas, as also under X-rays which should do so, shows that photoionisation in the gas phase is not fundamental to the production of $-\Delta i$. That the Δi occurs appreciably both within and well outside the region of selective absorption suggests (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 15, 175; Vishvanathan, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 21A, 300) that it is not a mere resonance effect; but some other type of quantal effect.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The results now reported, viz., the $-\% \Delta i$ increases (numerically) rapidly to a maximum, then decreases slowly and eventually changes sign, at large intensities of X-rays, can be explained on the behaviour of the space charge due to the positive ions in an ozoniser discharge (Part I, *loc. cit.*). It was shown therein on the essential analogy between an ozoniser discharge and the corona (the coaxial cylinder) that the discharge in the self-maintained region consisted of a number of high frequency current pulses due to the almost instantaneous electronic movement to the anode inter-spaced with ' t_m ', the time which is necessary for the traversal of the positive ions to the cathode (called the traversal time). This origin of the current pulses in the ozoniser discharge at and above the threshold potential V_m is similar to the Trichel pulses (*Phys. Rev.*, 1938, 54, 1078; 1939, 55, 382) observed in the corona. The application of the relation due to Montgomerys $i = Q/t_m$ and the suggested co-occurrence of $\pm \Delta i$ in benzene vapour (Part I, *loc. cit.*) are now discussed in the light of the mechanism of a counter.

On a careful examination of the current structure on the cathode ray oscillograph (208B Dumont) one finds that these current pulses can be grouped into two types (i) those having large and equal amplitude separated by approximately equal time intervals (ii) and those having relatively small and unequal amplitude appearing mostly between two consecutive pulses of class (i). These small pulses may be called satellite pulses and appear similar to the 'multiples' or 'spurious pulses' occurring in a counter (Wilkinson, "Ionisation Chambers and Counters", Cambridge Univ. Press, 1950, p. 225).

When the positive ionic space charge, left behind by the initial avalanches after choking the discharge, crosses the region of intense ionisation, limited by the critical radius r_c , the field near the inner electrode (anode) is partially restored. A stray electron, produced between the r_c and the anode, ionises cumulatively starting a fresh avalanche of its own, before the initial positive ionic space charge has been cleared. This gives rise to satellite pulse which is not of a full amplitude, on account of the presence of positive ionic space charge in the gap restoring the field partially. These satellites continue to occur until the initial ionic space charge is cleared off the discharge space. The initial positive ionic sheath reaching the cathode gives rise to cathodic electrons starting the normal full amplitude pulses. The satellites are favoured in an ozoniser discharge which has an extended r_c . The amplitude of the current pulses is due to the change in the potential of the inner electrode caused by the collected charge (Ramsay, *Phys. Rev.*, 1940, 57, 1022; Montgomerys, *ibid.*, p. 1030). The essential argument is not affected materially by considering the reversed polarity.

The simplified relation $i = Q/t_m$ (where Q is the charge collected by the anode and t_m = relaxation time) should include a factor ' t_a ', the active time, in denominator, during which mainly the electrons are collected. Because of the difference in mobilities of the electrons and ions, ' t_m ' is about a thousand time greater than ' t_a ' (which is of the order 10^{-8} sec.). Thus ' t_a ' can be neglected in comparison to ' t_m ' in a simple approximation for the study of a counter. In a complex current structure of an ozoniser the inclusion of this factor and the corresponding effect of irradiation during ' t_a ' and ' t_m ' becomes important for the understanding of Δi phenomenon.

The effect of irradiation may now be considered in two stages :

(1) *During the active time.* Its significance has been discussed in the earlier paper (this issue, p. 239).

(2) *Irradiation during 't_m'.* During this time, initial space charge (A) after crossing the critical radius r_0 , increases the field near the cathode. Irradiation during this time increases t_m due to enhanced positive space charge which favours the production of satellite pulses. This is supported by the observation of Fenton and Fuller (*Proc. Phys. Soc.*, 1949, 62, 32) that the probability for the occurrence of spurious pulses is accurately proportional to the charge generated in the discharge. This entails simultaneous occurrence of $+\Delta i$ during ' t_m ', due to increase in number (cf. Jatar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1950, 9B, 283) of satellites, and $-\Delta i$ as a result of the increase of ' t_m '.

Effect of X-ray Intensity and Frequency.—On the above view as the intensity of the X-ray irradiation is increased, more photoelectrons are ejected from the cathode leading to a greater decrease in α during ' t_a ', and resulting in larger $-\Delta i$. At a critical intensity, it may be expected that due to the additional positive ionic space charge α cannot decrease further, hence, the peak obtained in $-\Delta i$ with intensity variation. A further increase in intensity causing increase in the number of photoelectrons will presumably favour the production of satellites leading to an increase in the $+\Delta i$ component of the resultant effect.

As the frequency is increased, the photoelectrons emitted from the cathode will possess higher energy and consequently a greater reduction in α , as envisaged during ' t_a ' leading to larger $-\Delta i$.

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